

INNOVATION IN THE CREATION OF GEOMETRIC SHAPES. A NEW APPROACH TO OVAL DRAWING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14575043>

Abstract. Among the topics taught in "Engineering and computer graphics" of higher educational institutions, the topic "Oval creation of geometric shapes in axonometric, orthogonal, perspective, inclined, cylindrical and conical projections" is distinguished by its complexity. This article shows how to draw two vertical curves of an oval in a new and convenient way. Based on simple geometric principles, the proposed method allows to draw an oval more accurately and quickly. Also, this approach simplifies the calculations required in the process of making the oval. The advantage of the new method is that it provides an opportunity to accurately draw small ovals. If the size of the oval is small in the new drawing, drawing it involves some difficulties. Another advantage of the new style is that it works with the outer part of the oval, regardless of its size. With the help of this method, students will have the opportunity to fully and perfectly understand the topic at the level of 80-90%.

Keywords: point, frontal plane, horizontal plane, profile plane, curve, circle, radius, straight line.

Introduction

In the science of geometry, oval shapes have an important place because they are widely used not only in solving theoretical problems, but also in practice. There are currently orthogonal, axonometric, perspective, inclined, cylindrical and conical projection types. The oval is very widely used in these projection types [1]. I express the role of the oval in these types of projection and its dependence on life with the following: Orthogonal projection. Oval shapes are used in orthogonal projection, especially when indicating transverse or longitudinal sections. Application: As a cross-section of shafts or holes in machinery. In architecture: in the display of oval windows and arches. Axonometric projection: in isometric or dimetric form, the oval shape is used to depict the circular parts of a three-dimensional object.

Application: Technical drawings, pipes or objects with an oval cross-section. In design: in the design of oval panels or components. Perspective projection: the object is depicted in a shape, which decreases with increasing distance, and the shape of a circle becomes an oval in perspective. Application in art and architecture: interior design, oval constructions. In advertising and graphic design: drawing three-dimensional objects.

Oblique projection: oval shapes are depicted in this projection as particularly decorative and technical elements. Application: Technical drawings in rendering oval details at curved angles. Art and design: in the image of product prototypes. Cylindrical and conical projections: on maps, oval shapes can appear when showing geographic objects or models of planets. In mapping: Used in depicting the earth's surface in elliptical projections. There are many techniques for making an oval.

Literature Review and Methodologies. Currently, school and university textbooks explain the making of an oval using the book "Drawing in the 8th grade" by Ikrom Raimov. In school and

university curricula, the making of an oval is taught according to this order, and so far, no changes have been made to this method [2]. Again, there are a lot of similar methods. Scholars such as Apollonius of Pergae (262–190 BC), René Descartes (1596–1650), and Isaac Newton (1643–1727) carried on the design of the oval. All current methods are doing using the inner part of the circle when making 2 vertical curves of the oval. And the uniqueness of our style is found by using the outside of the circle.

Results. We have implemented a new and simplified way of creating an oval shape with the Kompas 3D software. The program helps us to increase our level of accuracy. This method greatly simplifies engineering graphics and drawings.

To learn how to process, it is important not only to draw an accurate and high-quality oval, but also to save time. To start the method, first of all, a point is taken from the plane. This point is taken as the center to form an oval shape, from which horizontal and vertical lines are drawn (Figure 1).

This point is, in fact, the center of the future circle, using which a circle is formed. The value of the circle can be optionally selected, but specific dimensions are usually given in assignments. In this way, in order to create an oval easily and conveniently, the value is randomly selected. Thus, a circle is drawn for the oval using a given point (Figure 2).

In the process of forming a circle, based on the center of the circle and its radius, determine the points where the "z" and "y" axis intersect. Through these points, curves are drawn from the center to the two extreme parts of the circle, which are connected to each other (Figure 3). These curves form the basic shape of the oval.

At the next stage, the process of connecting the curves intersected by the circle with straight lines begins (Figure 4). The points where these straight lines intersect with the circle are indicated by numbers, which allows for precise and convenient handling when creating an oval. Dots marked by numbers help to determine directions when forming an oval.

Picture 1.

Picture 2.

After that, the points where the circle intersects with its "z" and "y" axis are also denoted by numbers (Figure 5). A curve is drawn from point 5 to points 2-4, and also a curve is drawn from point 6 to points 1-3 (Figure 5). These curves help shape other parts of the oval. The distance from the junction of the resulting curves to the circle is determined, and a new circle for the oval is formed using that point (Fig. 6). This method allows you to create an oval accurately and correctly.

Picture 3

Picture 4

Picture 5

Picture 6

When a new circle is formed, the point where it intersects with the "y" axis of the large circle is called "b". A curve is drawn to points "a" and "c" using point "b" (Figure 7). This process forms the final form in the first half of the oval (Figure 8). On the other side of the circle of the oval by applying the same method, the final shape is formed (Fig. 9).

This method can be used both on the Frontal and Profile planes, which makes it possible to create drawings in different views.

Another convenient aspect of this new technique is that when drawing small ovals, the systems taught in university and school programs can sometimes lead to complications. For example, when deleting the auxiliary lines, there is a possibility that the oval itself will change incorrectly. However, our proposed method is recommended to use minimal utility strips when creating an oval. This will help preserve the integrity of the oval.

Discussion. The insufficient use of auxiliary bars when creating small-sized oval shapes helps to keep the oval in the correct shape and increases the sharpness of the image. At the same time, creating an oval in a simplified way will not only increase the accuracy of the initial drawn

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